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Qualitative Study on Integration of Multiple-Strategies for Effective Implementation of STEAM Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined Qualitative study on integration of multiple-strategies for effective STEAM instructional approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria. The study adopted Qualitative Research Method Specifically Systematics Literature Review. Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) are the vehicles for technological advancement and national development. STEAM is essential for the socio-economic development of any nation, including Nigeria, since it is aimed at meeting the aspirations of the individual and the society. Science and Technology have become the major ingredients of economic and national advancement it influences every aspect of our lives. They are centrals to our welfare as individuals and society at large. The position and prestige of a Nation in world politics depends on the extent to which the country advances in STEAM. STEAM are activities embarked by man in search of basic needs for survival on the planet such as food, shelter and clothing. It's on this note that the paper examined some impactful pedagogical approaches in STEAM, among which include: Anchored Instruction, Reggio Emilia Approach, Predict-Observe-Explain Instruction, Ethno-Science Instruction and Conceptual Change Approach. It was concluded that these approaches enhance effective teaching and learning. Finally, the paper suggested among others, that STEAM teachers should incorporate these approaches in teaching of Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) at secondary school level of Education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Identification. Impactful, Pedagogical Approaches, STEAM

Introduction

Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) are the only vehicles for technological advancement and national development Suleman (2010). Science and Technology have become the major ingredients of economic and national advancement. Science and Technology influence every aspect of our lives. They are centrals to our welfare as individuals and society at large. The position and prestige of a Nation in world politics depends on the extent to which the country advances in Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics. Omosewo (2006) defines Science as an activity which results into a testable, falsifiable and veritable body of knowledge. It accelerates the pace of change in the world by providing the foundation for wealth and development and brings improvement to the quality of life. STEAM is activities embark by man in search of basic needs for survival on the planet such as food, shelter and clothing. It is as old as man himself and meant for him to practice Lestari and Fitriani (2016).

The knowledge of Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) is relevant and applicable in all areas of life endeavors, without knowledge of STEAM, life on the planets would be miserable and primitive. For instance, the production of essential human needs such as soap of all kinds, creams, drinks, petroleum and its bi-products, clothing, drugs and household utensils and chemicals for preservations of food items as well as textiles are all a product of principles of science chemistry. While the productions and supply of energy from different sources, means of transportation, and communication as well as the inventions of machines and materials that make life comfortable and enjoyable as well as what makes work easier and faster are all products of the basic knowledge and principles of technological Physics. The knowledge of Biology is applicable in medicine, physiology and anatomy to preserve and save lives. The knowledge of Agriculture gives way for the production of food and animals which serve as meat and sources of protein as well as raw materials for industries.

The National Policy on Education (NPE) (2013), emphasized the importance of science and technology education at all levels of schooling, at the primary school level the objective of science education is to lay a sound knowledge in scientific and reflective thinking. There was inculcation of literacy and numeracy and the study of science and introductory technology. At the secondary school level, the aim is for the preparation of students for useful living in the society and for higher education. The

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objective of the science policy is to equip students with adequate scientific knowledge to live effectively in modern age of science and technology. To achieve this, integrated science is offered as a core subject at basic level (from primary one to the Junior Secondary School three) and science subjects (physics, chemistry biology) as parts of core subjects and technical subjects at the Senior Secondary School (SSS) level. At the higher education level the aim is the development of higher level manpower. Government policy at this level is that course content of science and technology is with professional career and it must reflect the national requirement through consultation among Universities (Babajide, 2015). Despite the importance of Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) in national development, the research works carried out by Omosewo (2001), Wokocha (2002), Olaniyi (2004), Adesoji (2008), Sulieman (2010) and Adeniran (2011), it has been stated that methods of instruction affect the performance of students in sciences and other related subjects. Hence, this study focuses on identifying some impactful pedagogical approaches in Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) and other related subject for effective teaching and learning.

Integration of Anchored Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Anchor instructional approach is one of the application models of constructivist approach, is a learning approach, which prescribes that all learning activities should be organized around a story, problem or case that is called anchor. This approach also provides the students with the opportunity to apply the information they have gained on different real-life cases and thus serves as a bridge between school life and real life. The materials within the border of programmes basing on anchor learning are generally technology-based and they contribute to students' success in a positive manner. Anchored instruction is a technology-based learning approach which stresses the importance of placing learning within a meaningful, problem-solving context. A form of situated learning, anchored instruction uses context-- stories or micro--- to situate the learning and application of knowledge. In other words, the learning is contextualized to provide students with realistic roles that serve to enhance the learning process.

Anchored instruction is a framework for learning that emphasizes complex problem solving in integrated learning contexts. Integrated learning contexts take on the form of drawing realistic connections, making learning meaningful for students, and

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forming connections within and between content domains. An anchored instruction activity supports learning opportunities that relate to and extend thinking to other content areas.

Learning and teaching activities are designed around an "anchor" which is often a story, adventure, or situation that includes a problem or issue to be resolved and that is of interest to the students. The "anchoring" refers to the bonding of the content within a realistic and authentic context: Anchored modules typically embed all of the information need— embedded data or hints are used as scaffolding— to solve the problem, making it easier to manage in environments with limited time or limited resources. Apart from creating specific contexts and scenarios, anchored instruction is also considered as an important approach to active learning which in particular stresses the importance of active involvement of learners, either mentally or physically, to achieve meaningful learning (Hativa 2000).

Pedagogical Foundations of Anchored Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The Group of Vanderbilt Cognition and Technology (CTGV) first developed anchor learning in 1990 under the leadership of John Bransford. Although many people have been contributing to the theory and research of anchor learning, the leader of this theory is Bransford. It evolved from the idea put forward by situated cognition which highlights the situated nature, that is, context specific feature of knowledge (Brown et al. 1989).

Anchor learning, one of the application models of constructivist approach, is a learning approach, which prescribes that all learning activities should be organized around a story, problem or case that is called anchor. This approach also provides the students with the opportunity to apply the information they have gained on different real life cases and thus serves as a bridge between school life and real life. The materials within the border of programmes basing on anchor learning are generally technology-based and they contribute to students' success in a positive manner.

Application of anchored Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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The primary application of anchored instruction has been to elementary reading, language arts and mathematics skills. The CLGV has developed a set of interactive videodisc programs called the 'Jasper Woodbury Problem Solving Series'. These programs involve adventures in which mathematical concepts are used to solve problems. It's applicable in a variety of problems. Whitehead claimed that learning environment produced memorized knowledge. On the other hand, anchor teaching is based on researching in laboratory and class, and thus tries to help the knowledge to be less memorized than the knowledge gained by means of traditional class activities such as remembering and exercise. This fundamental principle is a good example of structures' learning that emphasized the importance of inclusive learning. The techniques that help anchor teaching to be used effectively are target structures, students' active participation, content, applicability, awareness and cognitive apprenticeship.

Steps of implementing anchor Strategy in Classroom for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Bottge, (2002) identified seven steps to be considered when implementing an anchored learning in class, the following are steps to be followed when design anchored class; Choosing a field of study, Defining an anchor, Introducing the anchor, Discussing the anchor, Establishing groups and research questions and Running the research

Integration of Reggio Emilia Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Reggio Emilia Approach is a cooperative or interactive approach in which pupils do the learning by themselves and assist each other when the necessary materials are provided. It is a child-centered learning approach which involves children interacting with each other in the classroom and sharing ideas with one another. It also involves bringing in another teacher (instructor) to teach with the class teacher, thus enhancing efficiency. Reggio Emilia approach is an early childhood education which originated in Italy in 1945 after World War II.

In Reggio Emilia approach, classroom work is based on building the cognitive, social, language, creative and physical skills that empower pupils to gain and own learning experiences. Each child in the class has an opportunity to share, observe, play, learn and construct ideas on his/her own by visiting sites of interest provided in the

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corners of class- room which are full of open-ended materials like stones, sticks, bottle caps, blocks of many varieties and brain flatness in a collaborative approach. Children use their senses to explore and direct their educational experiences. They are given the freedom to select pre-prepared activities to work with. This means that they make incorrect attempts to solve a game or puzzle as classrooms are devised to be an ex- tension of children’s world. It is a pedagogy which focus-es on preschool and primary education. It was first developed in 1945 by psychologist Loris Malaguzzi and parents in the surrounding area of Reggio Emilia in Italy where the philosophy gets its name. They believed that children would benefit from a new and progressive way of learning (Owulabi, 2017).

The Reggio Emilia approach believes that children are capable individual that comes to school with wealth of experiences and knowledge and hence should be supported to communicate their ideas in a variety of ways. To the proponents, young children are powerful, active, and competent architects of their own growth, on the basis of their own particular experiences and level of consciousness. In a classroom where all resources and materials are thought provoking and inviting, the children are inspired to think critically and it provides children with a lot of learning opportunities that encourage them to explore, discover and solve problems on their own.

Reggio Emilia approach strongly believes that children learn through interaction with friends, parents, teachers as well as interactions with the learning environment. According to Kelemen, (2013), REA approach is committed to create learning conditions that encourage and facilitate the child to build his own power of thinking through the incorporation of the whole of expressive, communicative, and cognitive.

Pedagogical Foundation of Reggio Emilia Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The Reggio Emilia Approach derives its name from its place of origin, Reggio Emilia, a city located in Emilia Romagna in Northern Italy. Shortly after the Second World War, Loris Malaguzzi, a young teacher and the founder of this educational approach, joined forces with the parents of this region to provide care for young children. They felt that it is in the early years of development that children form who they are as individuals. This led to the creation of a program based on: the principles of respect, responsibility, and community; the value of exploration and discovery; a supportive and enriching environment; and the interests of the children through a self-guided

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curriculum. Originally inspired by the need of women to return to the workforce, over the last 50 years, this educational philosophy has caught the attention of early childhood educators worldwide.

Reggio Emilia is a town in the northern part of Italy. This area is the richest and most developed area of Italy with its population of four million people. This area is also the most-developed area of Italy which provides the social aid the most (Cited in Aslan, 2007 from Cadwell, 1997). This approach was supported by Louris Malaguzzi in Reggio Emilia city and emerged in preschool education institutions with the participation of families living in the area (Pekdogan, 2012). After the World War II, some families in the village of Villa Cella in Reggio Amilila town of Italy wanted to build a school for their kids and start the building of schools with the money they obtained by selling the tanks, trucks and horses remaining from the war. Reggio Emilia Municipal School was opened with the support of Malaguzzi and the families in question. With this approach, the city of Reggio Emilia was started to be mentioned as "the golden standard" in early childhood education (Pekdogan, 2012).

Application of Reggio Emilia Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Arseven, (2014) viewed Reggio Emilia as an alternative approach for educating children and generally it has the qualities of constructivist education generally. This approach, which aims for children to solve the problems he encounters himself, is also centered on children and family, society and teachers take part in this approach. It is necessary for a child to participate in activities himself and take part actively. Children growing up according to the Reggio Emilia approach become individuals with high self-confidence, improved personalities, improved production level who are acting in solidarity.

Reggio Emilia Approach is a method or approach to education, especially for young children. REA is different from other approaches. REA is committed to "create learning conditions that will encourage and facilitate the child to build up the strength of thinking itself through the incorporation of the whole of expressive, communicative, and cognitive" (Vecchi, 2010).

Children are encouraged to describe their understanding through one of the symbolic languages, including drawing, sculpture, dramatic playing, and writing. They work together to solve the problems that arise. The teacher facilitates and then observes

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the debate over the extent to which the child can solve the problem. Revising the drawings or ideas are performed if necessary, and the teachers let the children repeating the activity and modify each other's work for a collective purpose to be a better understanding of the topic. Teachers are involved in the exploration and evaluation process and pay attention to all children development outcomes in resolving problems based on their understanding.

Predict-Observe-Explain (POE) Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The POE learning model is a learning model with the knowledge development process, which begins with predicting solution over a problem, and then it goes with conducting experiment to prove the prediction, and finally it ends with explaining the result of experiment (White and Gystone, 2006). Kearney (2002) claims that POE learning model is a learning method, which involves the students to predict and discuss considerations for their prediction, to observe directly, and to compare the result obtained to their former prediction. This learning method makes the instruction more exciting and improves the conceptual mastery of the students.

Meanwhile, Tuckerman (2007) argues that POE learning model is a technique to ensure that the students articulate their former ideas with activities that lead them to understanding. The phases of the POE learning model include the following: (1) the students are introduced to a situation so that they are able to make predictions based on their experience; (2) the students are requested to make predictions and give reasons for their predictions; (3) the students do activity observations; (4) the students explain the differences between what they predict and the results of their predictions; and (5) the students are requested to propose new ideas to explain their understanding.

Predict-Observe Explain instructional strategy is a form of deductive reasoning, that is, reasoning from predictions to observation and it is significant in allowing learners to engage in learning tasks in small groups rather than the traditional teacher-led whole class environment. It allows learners to work at their own paces gives them the opportunity to go back and edit their initial responses and take control of the demonstrations. It makes learners to be autonomous and to thoroughly discuss and reflect on their predictions, reasons and observations. The observation phase of the

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instructional strategy is crucial and its effectiveness provides the feedback to learners on their predictions.

In regard to science learning, teachers can involve students to make hypotheses, investigate, and analyze data to develop students' thinking (Wardani, 2017). One model of learning that is capable of developing students' thinking optimally is Predict, Observe and Explain (POE) learning model. POE learning models can include ways that can be taken by a teacher to assist students in improving the understanding of the concept and their psychomotor. POE learning model engages students in predicting a phenomenon, observations through demonstrations or experiments, and finally explain the results of the demonstration as well as their hypothesis. By doing this way, acquired knowledge will be preserved in students' memory and increase students' science processing skills (Zulaeha, Darmadi & Werdhiana, 2014). To make an active teaching-learning process, students need to be able to clearly express themselves in written form and verbal form.

Pedagogical Foundation of POE Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Learning with a constructivist approach requires the use of various strategies and techniques. POE is one of the strategies included in this approach. This strategy is characterized by the steps of estimating, verifying predictions, defining observations, comparing and explaining predictions with observations, revealing students' prior knowledge, and allowing them to find alternative solutions to complex problems (Köse et al., 2003). It was first developed by Champagne, Klopfer, and Anderson in 1979 to measure the thinking skills of first-year physics students at the University of Pittsburgh. It was later given the name POE by White and Gunston in (1992).

The Predict-Observe-Explain instructional strategy has been described as a relatively new approach to the teaching of science (Zuziwe, 2006). Champagne, Klopfer and Anderson (1979) were the first to design the strategy as –Demonstrate-Observe – Explain (DOE). This strategy was initially used to probe the thinking of first year Physics students at the University of Pittsburgh. Gunstone and White reworked the DOE into Predict-Observe-Explain model (POE) in 1981.

The POE learning model can be used to recognize the initial ideas of students, to give information to the teacher about the students' thinking, to generate discussion, and to motivate them to investigate concepts (White and Gustone, 1992). The roles of the

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teacher in the POE learning method are as a motivator and a facilitator. As a motivator, the teacher is expected to be able to stimulate the students to solve problems through the following measures: (1) proposing relevant, challenging, and curious problems for the students, (2) trying to get the students cognitively active in each phase of the POE learning model; and (3) developing interaction among the students through questions and answers and discussions.

Stages of POE Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The Process of Predict-Observe-Explain Instructional Strategy consists of three procedural steps of prediction, observation and explanation phases. The Predict—Observe—Explain steps of Gunstone and White (1998) are:

Prediction Phase: Learners are presented with some questions to which they are expected to supply answers (predictions). They are also to give and discuss reasons for their predictions. It is a process to make a prediction toward a problem given by the teacher. In making the prediction, the students have thoughts the reasons why they make such a prediction. In this process, they are given an extensive freedom to arrange their prediction including its reasons. Therefore, the teacher should not limit the students' thoughts so that they produce many ideas and concepts. In this prediction process, the teacher can also understand the misconceptions made by the students. This is important for the teacher to help the students to develop right concepts.

Observation Phase: This is an experimentation phase where learners verify their predictions.

Activities here include reading textual materials and performing experiments in order to observe the real life situations or events in the laboratory. It is a process to investigate and observe what happens. In other words, the students are asked to do experiments to examine the prediction righteousness that they deliver. In this phase, the students do investigation or experiment to examine the prediction that they convey. The students observe what happens, and the most important thing in this measure is confirmation on their prediction.

Explanation Phase: Learners explain their observations and compare them with their initial predictions. Conceptual changes occur here and new knowledge or ideas

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are generated. There is rejection, acceptance or modification of learners' initial predictions as the case may be. It is a process to give explanation mainly the ones about the conformity between the prediction and the result of experiment of the observation phase. If the result of prediction is suitable with that of observation and after they obtain explanations about their prediction righteousness, the students will be more convinced about their concepts. However, when their prediction is false, the students can look for explanation why their prediction is not right. The students will experience the change of concepts from the false to the right ones. In this regard, they can learn from the mistake, and learning things from mistake will not be easily vanished or forgettable.

Integration of Ethno-Science Instructional Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Ethno-science instructional strategy involves the organization of instruction based on diverse cultural context. The strategy requires the teacher to draw analogy and explanations from traditional culture while focusing on the basic science needed by students in the society. Ethno-science instructional strategy according to Abonyi (2014) involves the teacher designing practical models of integration of indigenous and cosmopolitan knowledge systems with a view to achieving a balanced process of development and change. Ethno-science learning can transform teacher centered learning into centered on students as a contextual and meaningful learning (Sumarni, 2018).

Ethno-science is an interdisciplinary science that combines human and cultural anthropology with science education. The study of the scientific knowledge that is gained by examining the local knowledge that is contained in the culture of a community or ethnic group. Local awareness is derived from local communities' thought and ideas about daily life, including customs, beliefs and views on the world (Lestari & Fitriani, 2016). Ethno-science, rooted in students' lives, is a type of contextual experience (Setiawan et al., 2017). Ethno-science will allow students to investigate the facts and phenomena present in society and be integrated with scientific knowledge (Melyasari et al., 2018). Ethno-science can captivate learners because it's connected to their own regional identity. Ethno-science may also encourage knowledge and preserve local culture (Supriyadi & Nurvitasari, 2019). Ethno-science can make it easier for students to dig facts and phenomena that exist in society and can be integrated with science (Khoiri et al., 2019).

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Pedagogical Foundation of Ethno-science Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Ethno-science is a term and study that came into anthropological theory in the 1960s. Often referred to as "indigenous knowledge," it introduces a perspective based on native perceptions. Ethno-science looks at the intricacies of the connection between culture and its surrounding environment (Abonyi, 2002). The term ethno-science according to Okwara & Upu, 2017 refers to the materials, ideas, beliefs and technology in a given society or environment, that derive from the past and present cultural practices and traditions. It is knowledge that is indigenous to a particular people.

Snow (1972) reported that the integration of indigenous knowledge and ethno-scientific approaches into contemporary frameworks for instructions began around 1960 to 1965 with the works of Carl Hime, a supervising teacher for science and math at Many Farms High School, Many Farms, Arizona, United States of America. The emphasis in introducing Ethno-science at Many Farms then, was on life and ecological-environmental aspect of science.

The implementation of the ethno-scientific teaching approach is therefore based on the recommendations for teaching science by the Science for All Movement (UNESCO, 1991) which are:

- i. The content, language, symbols, designs, and purpose of the curriculum should be linked to day-to-day experiences and goals of the children;
- ii. Theory should be linked to practice, human purpose, the quality of life, and in-school experience to out-of-school experience; and
- iii. Teaching and learning should begin from the beliefs, interests, and learning skills that students bring to the classroom and should help each of them extend and revise their ability and understanding (Hiwatig, 2008).

Application of Ethno-Science Instructional Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Ethno-science instruction is applicable in science teaching, technology, elementary reading and arts. Ethno-science instruction is similar to the modified lecture method in terms of contents, basic instructional objectives, and mode of evaluation. The only

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differences are in the instructional activities and materials in which teachers in the ethno-science instruction group make use of additional information from common local beliefs and sayings stating their cultural meanings and relating them to science concepts being taught and learnt while also assessing and obtaining additional information from the learners and allowing them form their own opinion on the concept. Learners would also be allowed to utilize additional instructional materials reflecting local beliefs and expressions.

Conceptual Change Instructional Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Conceptual change instructional strategy is an instructional strategy in which the teacher acts as a facilitator by asking thought-provoking questions, conducting experiments, and leading guided discussions that help students think about constructing scientifically valid ideas. More specifically, it is a strategy that assists the student in distinguishing earlier conceptions and newly introduced scientific concepts, as well as how they impact each other as the learner quietly works out his ideas from the former idea and the newly introduced concept.

Conceptual change teaching as a learning approach that alters an existing conception, such as a belief, idea, or way of thinking. Conceptual change differs from other types of learning procedures in that it involves a shift or restructure of existing information and beliefs. Learning for conceptual change is more than just learning new facts or skills. An existing conception is significantly altered or even replaced in conceptual change, and this becomes the conceptual framework that students use to solve problems, explain phenomena, and function in their reality.

Conceptual change methodology, which is developed based on constructive approach and widely used in teaching-learning activities recently, considers students' previous knowledge and plans teaching activities based on this (Canpolat & Pınarbaşı, 2002; Dhindsa & Anderson, 2004; DiSessa, 2002; Mason, 2002; Uzuntiryaki, Çakır & Geban, 2001; Yürük, 2000). Conceptual change methodology represents an alternative approach that encourages students' to change their ideas from misconceptions to scientific correct facts (Broughton et al., 2010; Canpolat & Pınarbaşı, 2002).

Conceptual change approach that is commonly used in education recently takes students' previous knowledge into account and education program is planned based

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on these (Canpolat & Pınarbaşı, 2002; DiSessa, 2002; Dhindsa & Anderson, 2004; Mason, 2002; Uzuntiryaki et al., 2001; Yürük, 2000).

Pedagogical Foundation of Conceptual Change Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Conceptual change approach was proposed by Posner, Strike, Hewson, and Gertzog in 1982. Posner et al. in Özdemir and Clark (2007), described four necessary conditions (dissatisfaction, intelligibility, plausibility, and fruitfulness). Posner et al. in Özdemir and Clark (2007) proposed a model of conceptual change, which had four conditions, taking into cognizance the four conditions such as:

- i. Learners must become dissatisfied with their existing conceptions - they must have experiences, which lead them to lose confidence in the ability of their current conception to solve problems,
- ii. The new conceptions must be intelligible - the student must be able to understand sufficiently how experience can be structured by the new concept,
- iii. The new conceptions must appear plausible - any new concept adopted must at least appear to have the ability to solve the problems generated by its predecessors and,
- iv. The new conceptions must be fruitful - it should have the capacity to open up new areas of inquiry.

Conclusion

This study adopted a qualitative research method particularly systematic literature review on integration of multiple-strategies for effective STEAM instructional approach at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. The pedagogical approaches highlighted implement conceptual change in science teaching, emphasizing teaching for critical thinking and problem solving, encouraging teaching for transfer of learning, enriching socio-cultural learning, providing equal access for all participants in science.

Suggestions

In line with the review of the study, it is suggested that science teachers should:

1. Incorporate the use of Anchored Instruction as teaching strategy in teaching STEM.

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2. Reggio Emilia, Predict Observe Explain, Conceptual Change should also be used in teaching for easy understanding of STEM concepts.
3. Ethno-Science Instructional Approaches is a promising strategy for effective teaching and learning of STEM, it should be adopted.
4. Conceptual Instructional Approach is a very good approach to be adopted by STEAM teachers in Nigerian secondary schools for better understanding of concepts.

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